

Physical Properties and Chemical Constitution. Part II. Latent Heat of Evaporation, Density, Temperature, Surface Tension, and Composition of Organic Liquids

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A corresponding relationship similar to the one, postulated by the author previously¹, has been observed among the total heat of vaporisation (λ), the absolute temperature (T), the absolute critical temperature (T_c), and density of the liquid (D) and of its orthobaric vapour (d) at the corresponding temperature.

In a previous communication¹, which can be designated as Part I of this series, the author has described the relationship existing among internal latent heat of vaporisation (λ_i), the absolute temperature (T), the absolute critical temperature (T_c), and D and d , which are the densities respectively of the liquid and its orthobaric vapour at the corresponding temperature T . This relationship was utilised for the conception of lambdachor ($P\lambda_i$) which was found to possess some advantages over Sugden's parachor (P). A corresponding relationship has now been observed among the total heat of vaporisation (λ), the absolute temperature (T), the absolute critical temperature (T_c), and D and d . These relationships are :

$$\lambda = K(D-d)^{7/5} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$\lambda = K_1(T_c - T)^{0.42} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$D-d = K_2(T_c - T)^{0.3} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

The application of these empirical equations shows that the value of K , K_1 , and K_2 are constant for a particular liquid over a wide range of temperature.

If equation (i) is multiplied by the molecular weight (M) of the substance,

$$\frac{M}{D-d} \times \lambda^{5/7} = M \times K.$$

At low temperature, d is very small and can be neglected.

$$\therefore \frac{M}{D} \times \lambda^{5/7} = M \times K$$

$$\therefore \text{Molecular volume} \times \lambda^{5/7} = M \times K.$$

If we choose an arbitrary temperature, such as $\lambda^{5/7} = 1$, molecular volume (V_m) = $M \times K = P\lambda_a$ (lambdachor). As there are two lambdachors, one of which has been

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already described¹, may be called the *true lambdachor* ($P\lambda_i$), whereas the other can be called *lambdachor* ($P\lambda$). The values for atomic lambdachors and other constitutive effects are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Carbon	..	29.0	Oxygen (ethers)	..	270.0
Hydrogen	..	216.0	Oxygen (ketonic)	..	545.0
Nitrogen	..	146.0	O ₂ in esters	..	772.0
Double bond	..	308.0	6-Membered ring	..	99.0
Triple bond	..	614.0			

If the lambdachor ($P\lambda$) is a true measure of the molecular volume,⁷ there should be an intimate relationship among this constant, critical volume (V_c), true lambdachor ($P\lambda_i$), and Sugden's parachor (P). All these relationships are clearly shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Substance.	$P\lambda$.	$P\lambda_i$.	P .	V_c .	$P\lambda/V_c$.	$P\lambda/P\lambda_i$.	$P\lambda/P$.
1 Benzene	2456	1869	206.3	256.1	9.59	1.333	11.9
2 Diethyl ether	2561	1916	211.7	281.9	9.64	1.341	12.1
3 Ethyl acetate	2574	1962	217.1	286.0	8.99	1.322	11.9
4 Isopentane	2758	2081	230.0	307.8	8.99	1.321	12.0
5 Pentane	2816	2131	232.0	309.2	9.11	1.320	12.1
6 Ethyl formate	2218	1678	177.0	228.5	9.71	1.321	12.5
7 Propyl acetate	3085	2314	257.0	344.9	8.94	1.334	12.0
8 Ethyl propionate	3060	2295	252.9	343.9	8.90	1.334	12.1

Table II shows that the lambdachor ($P\lambda$) is nearly 12 times Sugden's parachor (P); for non-associated liquids, whereas it is approximately 9 times the critical volume (V_c), though it varies slightly from substance to substance. The ratio between the lambdachor ($P\lambda$) and the true lambdachor ($P\lambda_i$) is nearly 1.33, which is also the ratio between the specific heats of polyatomic vapour at constant pressure (C_p) and constant volume (C_v).

There is an intimate relationship among the lambdachor ($P\lambda$), the critical temperature (T_c), the critical volume (V_c), the entropy change (ΔS), and the boiling point (T_b) of an unassociated liquid and is expressed by

$$P\lambda = 6 \times \frac{V_c T_c}{T_b} = \frac{\Delta S}{3.463} \times \frac{V_c T_c}{T_b}$$

The basis of Sugden's parachor is the empirical relationship $\gamma^{1/4} \propto (D-d)$, postulated by Macleod², but the true lambdachor and lambdachor are based on the empirical relationships, $\lambda_i^{2/3} \propto (D-d)$ and $\lambda^{3/7} \propto (D-d)$, postulated by the present author. Combining these equations, it is possible to have a relationship among surface tension (γ), internal latent heat of vaporisation (λ_i), and latent heat of vaporisation (λ). These are $\lambda_i^{2/3}/\gamma^{1/4} = A$ and $\lambda^{3/7}/\gamma^{1/4} = B$, where A and B are constants over a wide range of temperature for most of the unassociated liquids. These equations enable us to determine the values of surface tension at definite temperatures, from the knowledge of the values of heats of vaporisation, A , and B and *vice versa*. These have been tested and found to be true.

It is very difficult to seek the physical significance of A , B , K , K_1 , and K_2 , but attempts are being made in this direction with the help of distinguished physicists. The Eötvös-Ramsay-Katayama equation³⁻⁵:

$$\gamma \times \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K (t_0 - t)$$

in the case of surface tension is applicable to the heat of vaporisation (λ) in the following form:

$$\lambda \times \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K (t_0 - t)^{0.22}$$

where K is independent of temperature over a wide range. The constant values of K for a particular liquid at different temperatures provide a new method for determining the molecular weight of nonassociable liquids. Moreover, just as Fergusson⁶ deduced Macleod's empirical relationship from Katayama's equation⁵, it is possible to deduce the empirical relationship:

$$\lambda = k(D-d)^{7/5}$$

from the same. The Eötvös equation has got the theoretical basis in the case of surface tension from the work of Madelung⁷, Born⁸, and Brillouin⁹. Surface tension and latent of vaporisation are different kinds of energy and what applies to surface tension can apply *mutatis mutandis* to latent heat of vaporisation.

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4. Ramsay and Shields, *Phil. Mag.*, 1893, 84, 647.
5. *Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1916, 4, 373.
6. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 19, 407.
7. *Physikal. Z.*, 1913, 14, 729.
8. *Ibid.*, 1913, 14, 731.
9. *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 1248.